

Complexes of Zinc(II), Cadmium(II), Lead(II), Copper(I), Silver(I) and Thallium(I) with 4-Amino-5-Mercapto-3-Trifluoromethyl-1,2,4-Triazole

R. V. GADAG and M. R. GAJENDRAGAD*

Department of Chemistry, Karnataka Regional Engineering College, Surathkal, P. O. Srinivasnagar-574 157, Karnataka

Manuscript received 10 October 1979, accepted 30 December 1979

Complexes of Zinc(II), Cadmium(II), Lead(II), Copper(I), Silver(I) and Thallium(I) with 4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-trifluoromethyl-1, 2, 4-triazole have been synthesised. The complexes are characterized based on analytical data, IR spectral studies, oxidation state study and magnetic susceptibility measurement. Tetrahedral structures are proposed for the complexes.

IN recent times, considerable interest is evinced in the study of complexing behaviour of mercapto derivatives of substituted 1,2,4-triazoles¹⁻⁵. In continuation of our previous work on metal complexes^{4,5} with substituted 1,2,4-triazoles, we report here the syntheses and characterisation of Zinc(II), Cadmium(II), Lead(II), copper(I), Silver(I) and Thallium(I) complexes with 4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-trifluoromethyl-1,2,4-triazole (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The ligand-4-amino-5-mercapto-3-trifluoromethyl-1,2,4-triazole.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AR or CP grade.

Preparation of the ligand: 4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-trifluoromethyl-1,2,4-triazole was prepared by the reported method⁶.

General method of preparation of complexes: A warm alcoholic solution of the ligand in slight excess over the molar ratio, was added to aqueous solutions of lead acetate or nitrates/sulphates of other metal ions. Ammoniacal medium was used in the case of Cd(II) and Zn(II) solutions. White crystalline complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II), Pb(II) and Tl(I) were formed readily. They were filtered after cooling, washed thoroughly with 50% alcohol, sparingly with ethanol and finally with ether. They

were dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 in a vacuum desiccator. All these complexes are fairly soluble in ethanol although they are almost insoluble in 50% alcohol. Complexes of Cu(I) and Ag(I) though white are not crystalline, but were formed readily. They were digested on water bath for 30 min. separated, purified and dried as described above.

Analyses:

Sulphur was estimated as BaSO_4 by alkali fusion method⁴. Metals were estimated by standard methods after destroying the ligand with Con.HNO_3 and heating to fuming with $\text{Con.H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Since micro analyses of C and H of fluorine containing complexes were not undertaken by any of the micro analytical sections in India, only the nitrogen analyses carried out on micro scale at CDRI, Lucknow, were used for determining the stoichiometry of the complexes.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) show that Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) form 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complexes while Cu(I), Ag(I) and Tl(I) form 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) complexes. The ligand readily reduces Cu(II) to Cu(I) and forms a stable Cu(I) complex. The +1 oxidation state of copper in its complex was confirmed by redox studies⁷. Further evidence in support of this comes from diamagnetic behaviour of Cu(I) complex.

Infrared Spectra:

Since the ligand molecule contains a thioamide moiety ($\text{H-N-C}=\text{S}$), it can exist in thiol as well as thione forms. A weak band at 2490 cm^{-1} in the IR

*For correspondence.

spectrum of the ligand suggests the presence of -SH group while a strong band at 790 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of C=S group. Since most of the metal ions under study belong to 'b' class or lie on borderline and some of them are highly polarizable, complex formation is greatly favoured at readily polarizable donor site viz. S where back bonding can occur. The IR spectral data lend support to this view.

The conspicuous absence of the $\nu(\text{S-H})$ band in the spectra of all complexes is an indication of bonding through thiol sulphur after deprotonation. Further evidence in support of this comes from systematic shifts in the thioamide band positions⁸ in the IR spectra of the complexes as compared with those for the ligand (Table 2). Thioamide band II [$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N}) + \delta(\text{N}-\text{H})$] appearing around 1250 cm^{-1} experiences a blue shift of about 30 cm^{-1}

support to sulphur atom being the site of coordination. In addition, the positions of thioamide bands I and III are considerably shifted towards lower wave number side. The IR bands in the region of $3100\text{-}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ of the primary amino group is slightly shifted towards lower number side. This indicates the participation of the N atom of the amino group in chelation with metal ions. Besides these observations, new bands around 400 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{M-N})$ and around 350 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{M-S})$ are also observed in the IR spectra of the complexes. These results are in Confirmity with the proposed mode of linkage. Based on the stoichiometry, IR data of the complexes and preferences of these metal ions for the tetrahedral geometry, tetrahedral structures are proposed for the complexes. However, two coordinate linear polymeric structures for Cu(I), Ag(I) and Tl(I) cannot be ruled out

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF LIGAND AND METAL COMPLEXES

Compound	N	Found % S	Metal	N	Calc. % S	Metal
$\text{C}_3\text{H}_3\text{F}_3\text{N}_4\text{S}$	30.13	17.47	-	30.43	17.48	-
$\text{Zn}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{F}_3\text{N}_4\text{S})_2$	26.12	14.85	14.93	25.96	15.14	14.85
$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{F}_3\text{N}_4\text{S})_2$	23.29	13.12	23.24	23.41	13.40	23.48
$\text{Pb}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{F}_3\text{N}_4\text{S})_2$	19.41	(11.46)*	35.98	19.54	11.18	36.13
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{F}_3\text{N}_4\text{S})$	22.58	13.15	25.74	22.71	13.00	25.76
$\text{Ag}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{F}_3\text{N}_4\text{S})$	19.31	11.20	37.05	19.25	11.02	37.07
$\text{Tl}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{F}_3\text{N}_4\text{S})$	14.55	7.97	52.53	14.46	8.27	52.74

*Found by difference.

TABLE 2—THIOAMIDE BANDS (IN CM^{-1}) IN THE LIGAND AND METAL COMPLEXES

Compounds	Band-I $\delta\text{N-H} + \nu\text{C}=\text{N}$	Band-II $\nu\text{C}=\text{N} + \delta\text{N-H}$	Band-III $\nu\text{C-N} + \nu\text{C}=\text{S}$	Band-IV $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$
LH	1580 S	1250 Ss	1090 Ss	790 ms
ZnL_2	1550 m	1275 Ss	1060 S	735 wb
CdL_2	1540 w	1285 ms	1065 ms	740 wb
PbL_2	1540 m	1275 S	1040 w	735 wb
CuL	1545 Ss	1275 Ss	1045 S	735 mb
AgL	1535 wb	1275 w	1055 w	735 wb
TlL	1540 mb	1265 ms	1040 mb	750 wb
Shift	red (35 ± 5)	blue (25 ± 10)	red (40 ± 10)	red (40 ± 15)

LH = $\text{C}_3\text{H}_3\text{F}_3\text{N}_4\text{S}$

S=strong, s=sharp, m=medium, w=weak and b=broad.

in the spectra of the complexes. This is a consequence of metal ion bonding through sulphur which would doubtless localize the double bond between C and N and shift the position of band II towards higher wave number side.

Thioamide band IV (Due mainly to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$) observed at 790 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand registers considerable red shift of about 40 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes. This lends additional

together although no definite evidence could be had to decide it conclusively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. K. Mahadevan, Principal and Prof. T. J. Varkey, Head of the Chemistry Department, Karnataka Regional Engineering College, for providing financial assistance, laboratory facilities and all round help.

References

1. B. K. SINHA, RAJESHWAR SINGH, J. P. SRIVASTAVA and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem. (U. K.)*, 1977, 39, 1797.
2. BIRENDRA KUMAR GUPTA, D. S. GUPTA, S. K. DIKSHIT and U. AGARWALA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 624.
3. BIRENDRA KUMAR GUPTA, D. S. GUPTA and U. AGARWALA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. (Jap.)*, 1978 51, 2724.
4. R. V. GADAG and M. R. GAJENDRAGAD, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16A, 703.
5. R. V. GADAG and M. R. GAJENDRAGAD, *Curr. Sci.* 1979, 48, 839.
6. T. GEORGE, R. TAHILRAMANI and D. A. DABHOLKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 959.
7. D. BANERJEA and I. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 6, 34.
8. B. SINGH, R. SINGH, R. V. CHAUDHARY and K. P. THAKUR, *J. Indian, Chem.*, 1973, 11, 174.